

The Discarded Humbug | Carryall

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26–33 minutes

Kevin B. Sheets responds to Chapter 3—From Republican to Romantic (1800-1850) in Jennifer Ratner-Rosenhagens *The Ideas That Made America: A Brief History*.

What's In the Give-Away Bin?

Jennifer Ratner-Rosenhagen has gone all Marie Kondo on the American intellectual tradition. In her justly influential 2019 book *The Ideas that Made America*, Ratner-Rosenhagen pares down, culls, and tidies. Her history is neat and smart like Kondo's pantry. The chapter on the period from 1800 to 1850, for example, guides readers from Republicanism to Romanticism with curated stops at "higher criticism," "transcendentalism," and "the South," before ending with Margaret Fuller as Emerson's "Man Thinking." There is neither dust nor clutter here. Her history feels spacious, even spare, like a Kondo bookcase.

I appreciate her kempt account, but I'm also the kind of guy who wonders what Kondo tossed into her give-away bin. Ratner-Rosenhagen's streamlined history from Republicanism to Romanticism hews closely to the texts Capper and Hollinger canonized in *The American Intellectual Tradition*, a two-volume set that I have assigned for years. Her topography is familiar: we are at the Divinity School listening to Emerson; on the lyceum stage with Horace Bushnell; and in the offices of *The Dial* with Margaret Fuller. Here is largely the typical New England story, with a side trip to Virginia. Her approach prioritizes a particular narrative, which we might summarize as a question: how do we know? For the early republican generation, the answer drew from an Enlightenment confidence in human reason. A knowable universe of truths existed, waiting to be uncovered and perceived by the senses. Not surprisingly, that generation took up natural history, experimented with electricity, and hypothesized natural laws governing politics, the economy, and the sciences. They wrote encyclopedias and kept commonplace books to organize facts.

At the same time, they eschewed the fantastic. Thomas Paine proclaimed an "age of reason" when he rejected Christianity's moral authority. William Ellery Channing promoted a more rational Christianity in the form of Unitarianism. Channing prefaced his 1819 ordination sermon for the Rev. Jared Sparks with a passage from I Thessalonians: "Prove all things; hold fast that which is good." When speaking of scripture, he accepted "without reserve or exception" those doctrines which were "clearly taught." But the Bible was, after all, a text. "We do not, however, attach equal importance to all the books in this collection." Similarly, Jefferson clipped the miraculous from the New Testament, leaving Jesus in the tomb.

While confident in their power to ascertain Truth, Jefferson's generation also knew such work took discipline. No doubt, it is one of the reasons so many esteemed the study of Latin in schools and colleges; they believed conjugating dead verbs concentrated the mind. The resulting mental discipline fitted one for enlightened and self-sacrificing republican citizenship. They worried,

however, that not everyone's reason could resist the temptations of passion. The republican system, therefore, came with guardrails. Checks and balances, federalism, the electoral college, and property qualifications for suffrage all insulated government from the vagaries of a citizenry that might yield not to the "better angels" of their nature, but to their vices.

So long as the pursuit of Truth required discipline, the founding generation could allay their anxieties by placing their faith in the tempering qualities of social and cultural (to say nothing of political) hierarchy. But that discipline dissipated in the face of democratizing forces, and by the 1830s, the masses were less willing to bend to the parental hands that had once schooled them. This rising generation took to heart the implications of the Enlightenment faith in humankind's abilities and the democratization of knowledge. They too had senses that could perceive the Truth, so what need had they for mediators? Similarly, the gospel truth of evangelicalism shifted their relationship with God. The Calvinist God who predestined one's fate faded, replaced by an evangelical God who offered men and women of free will the gift of grace to accept or reject according to their pleasure. Ministers and the church structure might be nice, but neither were necessary. One could go it alone.

Going It Alone

In fact, going it alone was precisely what Ralph Waldo Emerson preached. In his address to the graduating students at Harvard's Divinity School, Emerson "admonished" them to "go alone; to refuse the good models, even those which are sacred in the imagination of men, and dare to love God without mediator or veil." With the panicked faculty listening in, Emerson warned the "newborn bard[s] of the Holy Ghost" that the "imitator dooms himself to hopeless mediocrity." Emerson urged an immediate, living, and true experience, not one served secondhand from books, lectures, or ritual.

Transcendentalists such as Emerson were influenced (ironically?) by their reading of the Romantics, who sought Truth not from the evidence of the senses but from the promptings of the spirit. In that same address to graduating students, Emerson identified a new standard. "The intuition of the moral sentiment," he told them, "is an insight of the perfection of the laws of the soul." One's intuition, or gut instinct, measured the truth of a thing, not the fallible senses and certainly not tradition or habit. Emerson also spoke of the laws of the soul, not the laws of nature. His truths were his. "These laws execute themselves," he noted. "They are out of time, out of space, and not subject to circumstance." In "Self-Reliance," Emerson told his audience to "trust thyself: every heart vibrates to that iron string."

Ratner-Rosenhagen traces the arc from Republicanism to Romanticism. In one sense, both republicanism and romanticism taught ways of knowing. Trust the senses to discern nature's truth. Trust thyself. Yet, in either case, republicans and romantics sought Truth. They both trusted in truth's existence, either "out there" or in one's soul. Both republicans and romantics were so earnest because the stakes were high. Republicans were betting on the viability of the new nation while romantics cultivated the self's independence and integrity.

This is a very nineteenth century story, one marked by confidence. The century began with a revolution announcing a new truth about the individual's natural rights. It marched ahead with faith in his or her perfectibility. It closed confident still in their ability, employing tools from the natural and social sciences, to usher society into a progressive age.

Shooting Hoops

That is a good story, and it makes sense of the raw materials we typically use when crafting an intellectual history of the period. But what if we embraced what Ratner-Rosenhagen preached (but did not quite practice) and use evidence other than the “traditional sources of intellectual history (works of philosophy, political and social theory, literature, and cultural criticism)”? What if we took seriously her desire to come “into contact with interesting people we might not otherwise know” to include even people who did not write works of “philosophy, political and social theory, literature, and cultural criticism”? Would we still be practicing “intellectual history”—or something else?

When I was in graduate school, some buddies and I rented a house literally “on the other side of the tracks” from the grounds of the University of Virginia. Our neighbors were some of the “interesting people” whom Ratner-Rosenhagen might have wanted to know. We got to know two of them because they sometimes came over to shoot hoops in our living room, dribbling and tossing our Nerf basketball, passing to one of us, and slinging insults. They were cousins. Two black boys, ages eight and ten. During one of these games, the ten-year old called to his cousin: “You government cheese-eating faggot.” The eight year old replied: “Least I don’t wear no twenty-five cent Converse.” The older boy responded: “Least I GOT twenty-five cent.”

I have often thought of this exchange. I recount it to my students every time I teach my course on American intellectual and cultural history. The anecdote reminds me of the limitations of both social and intellectual history. The social historian might locate these boys within a matrix of social science and local, state, and federal statistics, or demographic and residential data. Perhaps their names appear in Charlottesville’s family court or social services records. School records might tell us something about them. But the social historian might not penetrate into their inner lives. Instead, we might know them as aggregated data revealing in broad strokes the plight of poor African American youth in the 1990s South.

For the intellectual historian? Well, good luck. These boys likely did not leave the sort of evidence that typically catches the attention of intellectual historians. No treatises or essays. No works of criticism or literature. We probably have no written records from their own hands at all. Their youth predated tweets and posts and Tik Tok videos, so even those traces are not available. For the intellectual historian, these boys are ghosts, their intellectual history is invisible, unrecoverable. Yet, they had an intellectual history worth knowing. If we think of intellectual history, as Ratner-Rosenhagen does, as an investigation of the power of ideas to shape lives, then thinkers such as these boys should be our focus as much as Emerson or Fuller.

When I first heard the exchange between cousins, I was taking a cultural history class with James Gilbert, who, for reasons I can’t remember, was teaching that semester at UVA. I wrote about these boys, intoxicated with the idea that cultural history was the intellectual history of ordinary folks. Here was a method that mined the anecdote, the fleeting phrase, the joke and gesture to recover a lost world of assumptions, values, anxieties and hopes not otherwise accessible to us. “You government cheese-eating faggot” was rich with interpretive possibilities. This ten year old boy had already experienced the intimacy of the federal government, the way it directly entered his home and, indeed, his body. His language revealed assumptions he had already formed about dependency and masculinity. His cousin’s rejoinder about Converse sneakers betrayed his absorption within, maybe his entanglement by, a powerful consumer culture. This snippet of conversation was their essay, their treatise, their work of literature and criticism. They had an intellectual history, and we could glimpse it.

With the tools of cultural history in place, what if we returned to the period from republicanism to

romanticism and tried to catch sight of the gesture and to hear the joke? Does the punchline tell us something new about the period, something not already visible in Emerson's essay or Channing's sermon? How might folk, vernacular, or popular culture serve as intellectual history too? What if, for example, we framed the period from republicanism to romanticism as a period not from Jefferson to Emerson, but rather from Peale to Barnum. What if we sought the American intellectual tradition inside Charles Willson's Peale's paintings and the American Museum he created? What if we took P.T. Barnum seriously as an American intellectual? Barnum purchased the remnants of Peale's Museum in the 1840s. What if we expanded the Capper and Hollinger canon to include the museum and the hoax?

The Museum

Beginning with Peale (1741-1827) is also beginning with Republicanism. Born during the American enlightenment, Peale embodied that era's ideals and aspirations. A polymath like so many of his generation, including Benjamin Franklin, Benjamin Rush, and Thomas Jefferson, Peale had intersecting talents and interests. A saddler by training, Peale taught himself how to make and repair watches. He became involved in politics and then joined the Continental Army, attaining the rank of captain. He fought at the battles of Trenton, Princeton, and Germantown. He subsequently served in the Pennsylvania legislature. It was his talents as an artist, however, that brought him lasting fame. Before the Revolution, he developed an interest in painting. Through the generosity of local patrons, he traveled to London to study under Benjamin West, the American expatriate whose career as a court painter George III advanced. In 1772, Peale painted the first known portrait of George Washington. Over the next several decades he painted a congress of early American worthies, peopling Americans' visual culture with images of their political, military, and civic leaders. Many of these portraits were displayed in the Philadelphia museum he created in 1802. The Peale Museum, the first such institution in the United States, brought together his varied interests in the arts and sciences. It became an anchor for Philadelphia's civic culture.

Charles Willson Peale, *The Artist in His Museum*, 1822.

Near the end of his life, Peale completed a large canvas, a self-portrait in his museum. At eight and a half feet tall and six and a half feet wide, the painting depicts the artist ensconced within what can only be described as a republican temple of knowledge. Peale pulls back a heavy red drapery allowing visitors entry into his organized museum. Along the walls Peale has displayed representative examples of the young republic's bounty. Each case contains taxidermized specimens organized according to Linnaeus's classification system. Atop these cases, visitors can see Peale's exhibit of portraits. Just behind him and partially obscured by the drapery stands the mastodon. Its skeletal form perhaps reminded Peale's guests of his early triumph. In 1801, Peale funded the exhumation of the mastodon, an event he commemorated in another immense canvas completed between 1806 and 1808. In the background of his museum portrait, well-heeled visitors—a father and his son, a contemplative man with folded arms, and nearer to us a young woman who appears to have just taken in the immensity of the mastodon display—engage in republican uplift. Peale's museum is nothing if not an incubator of civic virtue and enlightenment.^[1]

The painting, *The Artist in His Museum*, completed in 1822, is perhaps the summation of Peale's life work, but it is also emblematic of the republican culture Peale inhabited and helped nurture. Peale's invitation signals the republican motivation to secure the young nation's future by educating its citizens. The painting, like the museum itself, was a school. Culture was didactic more than entertaining. Patrons of the museum were supposed to appreciate the revealed truths of the universe visible in the organized display of fossils, flora, and fauna. This was almost sacred space, a point perhaps Peale himself pushed with the inclusion of the heavy curtain. One wonders if viewers connected the drapery image with Matthew's Gospel. The temple curtain was rent asunder at the exact moment when Jesus breathed his last. The temple curtain had prevented ordinary people from experiencing the immanence of God, but its destruction opened holy knowledge to them. Similarly, Peale's drawing of the curtain gave access to the wisdom of God's creation.

Peale's painting and the museum it depicted also reflects the individualism of the age. Jefferson, of course, had proclaimed as self-evident the right to pursue happiness and the genius of the revolution was the loosening of bonds and the ennoblement of the individual. Still, too much individualism panicked the founding generation. Their preference was for an individualism tempered by a moral and social commitment. All their labored talk of virtue betrayed this anxiety. The virtuous citizen, they hoped, exercised his liberties in service of the common good, rather than to satisfy his self-indulgences. Republican culture, of the sort showcased in Peale's museum, disciplined the self, restrained passions, and channeled actions into civically useful pursuits.

By the time Peale's painting dried, and certainly by the time P. T. Barnum purchased the remnants of Peale's museum in the 1840s, this idealized republican culture was already transforming. Historians used to describe what came next as the Age of Democracy, though we have come to recognize the limits of that democratization. Still, the development of the market economy, the slowly expanding franchise, and the spread of evangelical Christianity together eroded the hierarchies that had stabilized, and constrained, social relationships. Unleashed from republican discipline, a more self-serving individualism could flourish. The market encouraged the entrepreneur. Evangelical Christianity preached a gospel of free will, and by rejecting the Puritans' terrorizing predestination doctrine, grace became a gift offered by a loving Father. If they could now choose to accept the gift of grace and the election into heaven it presumed, denying the franchise in elections for sheriff, mayor, and representative made no sense. The self became the measure of all things.

The Hoax

Peale represents early American republicanism, but—and here is the key divergence from Ratner-Rosenhagen's beautifully minimalist portrayal—the shift to Barnum leads us not to Romanticism but to someplace else. I would like to explore the possibility that Barnum's museum and his various exhibits and hoaxes uncover the presence of a barely visible postmodern culture emerging within the seemingly confident expression of nineteenth-century America.

It may seem perverse, and surely ahistorical, to posit a postmodern twist prior to modernism's turn. Nevertheless, Barnum's contributions to American cultural life, though easily dismissed as "humbug," surfaces a puckish attitude toward truth and representation. His subversive complicity blurred the line between stage and audience. Barnum's patrons were enlightened and willing fools. They were in on the joke. He seduced them with the hoax, and they enjoyed the seduction. Indeed, Barnum made them co-conspirators. They were themselves like Joice Heth, the supposed 161-year old black nurse of the infant George Washington, and the Feejee Mermaid, the part-woman, part-fish mutant, to name two of Barnum's more infamous displays: patrons, yes, but also exhibits themselves. Barnum displayed his audience's credulity and its incredulity. And he told them he was doing it. Barnum went meta when meta wasn't cool.

There is a rich literature on Barnum as a nineteenth century cultural icon. Much of this work explores Barnum's career as a showman and cultural entrepreneur. His own memoirs and autobiographies lean into his identity as the "prince of humbug." Taking his cue, these biographies have narrated his exploits, positioning Barnum within a nineteenth century popular culture matrix defined by the emerging urbanism and communication revolutions that supported the development of a middling class. More recent works have interrogated Barnum's trade on racialized tropes in his appeal to middle class audiences. Benjamin Reiss' *The Showman and the Slave: Race, Death, and Memory in Barnum's America* uses Barnum's Joice Heth hoax to reveal bone-deep racial norms endemic to northern antebellum middle-class audiences.^[2]

Most intriguing is James W. Cook's fascinating study of the "artful deceptions" of nineteenth century America. His book, *The Arts of Deception: Playing with Fraud in the Age of Barnum*, situates the "prince of humbug" within a longer history of tricksters, but he reveals the peculiar and unique qualities of fraud which flourished in the emerging market society Barnum exploited. Cook moves beyond narratives of humbug, however, to offer a provocative thesis concerning Barnum's "modernism." Cook suggests Barnum-era deceptions constituted a "slippery mode of new middle-class play," signaling Barnum's patrons' own willing complicity in the fraud. In his telling, these

frauds were less about discerning the truth or fakery of a hoax. What Barnum taught his audiences was to live with the ambiguity. Barnum's hoaxes "held out the promise of truth," Cook writes, "but they also helped socialize their audiences to a brave new world in which the very boundaries of truth were becoming more and more puzzling."³

This contested boundary is often elided in conventional narratives of nineteenth century intellectual history. No doubt that is a function of the cast of characters constituting that narrative. If we include Barnum as a legitimate constituent of America's intellectual tradition, however, then the boundary-defying blurring his hoaxes performed may reveal the existence of epistemological ambiguities in the 1830s and 1840s. Is it too much to suggest that Barnum, in addition to entertaining his audience also, consciously or not, led them to face the possibility that Truth was a fiction? More to the point, was knowing possible? Both Peale and Emerson believed it was, although they understood authority in different ways. Peale hung on to knowing. Barnum seemed not to care, and he perhaps urged his patrons not to care either. Barnum was post-Truth. He was postmodern.

Being Duped

Barnum evokes postmodernism more than pragmatism, another conventional stopping point in the history of American intellectual culture. Pragmatism shared an earnestness with republicans and romantics. It was serious stuff. Pragmatists employed method to determine the truth of an idea by looking at its effects. For Charles Peirce and William James, late nineteenth century's leading pragmatists, an idea became true when it worked. While James accepted the possibility of more than one truth, he still sought truth. Barnum's interests lay elsewhere in the playful give and take between representations. Barnum's career in the 1830s and 1840s might argue for an earlier Gilded Age if we think of that latter nineteenth-century period as one defined by layers, facades, and patinas.

The Joice Heth hoax may illustrate the point. The contours of the story are well-known. In 1835 Barnum took control of an exhibit: a woman represented to be the 161-year old black nurse of the infant George Washington. Barnum intuitively appreciated the cultural resonance (and potential profit) Joice Heth's story had in the 1830s. The founding generation had, by then, all passed away. Charles Carroll of Carrollton, the last living signer of the Declaration of Independence died three years before Barnum bought Heth and presented her to audiences. "Founding nostalgia" had settled in and Heth represented a living connection to the greatest of all the founders. As both Cook and Reiss note, northern white audiences also projected onto Heth's body their racialized assumptions and stereotypes. She was also depicted as a physical curiosity, an ancient relic, a "freak" that defined for middling audiences the "respectable" line separating them from others.

Poster advertising Joice Heth, ca. 1835.

Barnum displayed Heth in New York and hoodwinked the commercial press into hyping his exhibit. And the people came. Barnum made a show of documents authenticating details of Heth's life including a bill of sale signed by Washington's father and testimony of doctors affirming her age. Audiences were invited to poke and prod. Heth seemed to play along. She regaled audiences with stories of young George and sang hymns. When the exhibit moved to Boston and attendance began to flag, Barnum shifted tactics. He planted stories in the unwitting newspapers alleging Heth was a hoax. Counterintuitively, Barnum's ruse drove increased interest. People came back for a second look. Was she real, or a machine? When Heth died in February 1836, Barnum kept the exhibit going in a revised form. He offered (paying) customers the chance to witness her autopsy, which determined she was half the age she was represented to be. Barnum was astonished, giving the impression that he himself had been duped.

Being duped was part of the fun. Barnum leaned into the humbug. He was careful to distinguish humbug from a scam, however. Barnum was not a con man. The hoaxes he perpetrated may have playfully deceived, but patrons still got their money's worth. They derived entertainment value from observing Heth and wondering if she really were 161 years old, knowing full well the absurdity of it all.

Barnum's use of language is key here. In his advertising, he said Heth was "represented" to be 161 years old. Barnum exploited the gap between representation and the thing represented. In the

same way structuralists would speak of the signifier and the signified, which revealed the arbitrary nature of language and the conventions we embrace to facilitate meaning, Barnum's hoaxes playfully hypothesized the arbitrariness of what was represented to be fact. Peale presented his museum as self-evident truths. Barnum instead encouraged skepticism. He even planted articles purposefully to raise doubt. In trumpeting his Feejee Mermaid hoax, he unmasked authority. "Many naturalists and scientific men who have examined it," he told his audiences, "assert that it is absolutely the work of Nature. Others however insist that its existence is a natural impossibility." Conventional sources of authority failed. "When doctors disagree," he concluded, "the PUBLIC must decide." Truth was individual. It was contingent. It was what the individual said it was. And perhaps, it was nothing at all.

More Escher than Kondo

Traditional intellectual histories of the period are so serious. One wonders if any of the intellectuals Ratner-Rosenhagen profiles ever laughed. Does it have to be that way? If we expand the cast of characters to include Barnum and take his cultural productions seriously as artifacts in America's intellectual tradition, does the history of this period from Republicanism to Romanticism change? The history is certainly less linear. It is also more complex. Peale and Emerson proclaimed truths. But Barnum taught his patrons to live with ambiguities: to raise the eyebrow, to second guess, to laugh. One might credit Barnum with softening the ground for Darwin's revelations concerning a universe of chance and contingency. The world is not what we expected. Its representations are often constructed narratives and those constructions can be deconstructed, turned inside out, reframed, and playfully poked and prodded. By supposing a postmodern turn, we glimpse the era's indeterminacy. We see characters playfully making meaning. We might also restore a sense of joy and wonder to the period we have otherwise laden with seriousness, purpose, and duty.

We need an intellectual history of the early to mid-nineteenth century whose inspiration is more Escher than Kondo. Barnum teased his audience with the artful deception. Like an Escher drawing, Barnum guided patrons along an impossible staircase. He took delight in their broadening smiles as they slowly warmed to the reality of the misdirections and illogical, impossible pleasures they evoked. In the so-called Age of Emerson, Barnum exploited the gaps between the legitimate and the illicit, the represented and the representation, to usher in a modern (and perhaps even a postmodern) turn. Like his sleights-of-hand, this larger intellectual pivot is easy to miss. We should paw through Kondo's give-away bin. The discarded humbug of cultural history might be just the piece we've been looking for to make better sense of intellectual history.

About the Author

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Notes

[1] For an analysis of Peale's mastodon painting see, Eleanor J. Harvey, "Founding Landscape: Charles Willson Peale's Exhumation of the Mastodon," *American Art* 31 (Summer 2017): 40-42.

[2] Benjamin Reiss, *The Showman and the Slave: Race, Death, and Memory in Barnum's America* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2001).

[3] James W. Cook, *The Arts of Deception: Playing with Fraud in the Age of Barnum* (Cambridge,

MA: Harvard University Press, 2001), 28.

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